

D10.6 – Dissemination report

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Abstract: Report on the CLEANDEM D&C activities implemented during the project lifecycle and foreseen after the project end. In this regard, the report regroups all the D&C activities (publications, presentations, social media, etc.) conducted and planned during the CLEANDEM lifecycle.

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PU	Public	X
RE	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the Consortium (including the Commission Services)	
TN	Technical Note	

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Glossary

Acronym	Description	Acronym	Description
D&C	Dissemination and Communication	FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable
D&D	Decommissioning and Dismantling		

Purpose of the document

Report on the CLEANDEM D&C activities implemented during the project lifecycle and foreseen after the project end. In this regard, the report regroups all the D&C activities (publications, presentations, social media, etc.) conducted and planned during the CLEANDEM lifecycle.

1 Introduction

The CLEANDEM consortium has considered D&C activities to be crucial in contributing to the exploitation of the project results and learnings by a much larger scope of stakeholders than the project consortium.

In fact, the project partners acknowledge that the CLEANDEM research and new knowledge generated could potentially contribute to address societal, industrial, scientific and political challenges in the D&D domain. As such, the foreground knowledge has been communicated and disseminated throughout the project duration according to FAIR principles and building on the vision of open access to publications and, to the extent possible, data, which are respectively the scope of the CLEANDEM Data Management Plan (D10.4). In this regard, while implementing the D&C activities presented in this report, the CLEANDEM partners have resorted to the [Zenodo repository](#) for sharing the CLEANDEM outputs and results with larger audiences.

Within this framework, this report will detail all the D&C activities implemented and planned by the project partners during the CLEANDEM lifecycle.

2 Dissemination activities

The dissemination implemented throughout CLEANDEM have aimed to make sure that the projects results could be available to the scientific community, policy makers and industry using scientific language prioritizing accuracy. In order to make it possible, the CLEANDEM project partners have planned and implemented the dissemination activities detailed in the following sub-paragraphs.

2.1 Events

Throughout the CLEANDEM lifecycle, all the project partners both participated to key events and conferences aiming to sponsor the project results as much as possible, and to reach stakeholders and potential partners for CLEANDEM and future EU-funded projects. Namely, this sub-paragraph will refer to national and international conferences (2.1.1) and to events aimed to establish synergies with other EU-funded projects (2.1.2). Moreover, a paragraph is dedicated to the Final Workshop (2.1.3), which represents a key project milestone jointly and successfully organized by all the CLEANDEM project partners.

2.1.1 National and international conferences

The following table includes all the events attended by the CLEANDEM project partners throughout its entire duration, by also including the type(s) of dissemination activity/activities implemented.

Participating partners	Event	Type of dissemination activity	When
CEA	DigiDECOM 23	Participation and CLEANDEM advertisement	Oct-23
CEA, Orano DS, CAEN, INFN	ANIMMA 2023	Leaflets' distribution and INFN presentation	Jun-23
CEA, AiNT, CAEN	ICOND 2021	Exhibition booth and leaflets' distribution	Nov-21

CEA, CAEN	IAEA "Int. Conf. on Rad. Waste Management: Solutions for a Sustainable Future"	Participation and CLEANDEM advertisement	Nov-21
CEA	DigiDECOM 24	Participation and CLEANDEM advertisement, combined with presentation of XS-ABILITY, follow-up of CLEANDEM work	Nov-23
CAEN	IEEE-NSS 2022	Exhibition booth and leaflets' distribution	Nov-22
CAEN, SOGIN	IAEA "International Conference on the Safety of Radioactive Waste Management, Decommissioning, Environmental Protection and Remediation: Ensuring Safety and Enabling Sustainability"	Leaflets' distribution	Nov-23
CAEN, AiNT	ICOND 2022	Exhibition booth and leaflets' distribution	Nov-22
ENEA	ICRM 2025	Participation and CLEANDEM advertisement	May-25
ENEA	RAD 2024 Conference	Participation and CLEANDEM advertisement	Jun-24
INFN	IAEA General Conference 67th	Participation and CLEANDEM advertisement	Sep-23
INFN	IAEA General Conference 66th	Participation and CLEANDEM advertisement	Sep-22
INFN	IAEA Safeguards	Participation and CLEANDEM advertisement	Oct-22
INFN	SOGIN techpark workshop	Participation and CLEANDEM advertisement	Jan-23
INFN	Meeting with the Italian Physical Society	Participation and CLEANDEM advertisement	Sep-24
SOGIN	SFEN International Conference on Decommissioning Challenge (DEM 2024)	Leaflets' distribution	May-24
CSM SPA	Big Science Business Forum (BSBF) 2024	Poster	Oct-24

2.1.2 Synergies with other EU-funded projects

The CLEANDEM consortium actively participated to key meetings of other EU-funded projects working in the field of unmanned operations in the nuclear field, such as INNO4GRAPH and MICADO. Namely, the table below shows the meetings attended :

Participating partners	Event	Type of dissemination activity	When
CEA, ENEA, SOGIN	MICADO Final Demonstration	Participation	Jan-23
CEA, SOGIN, ARTTIC	INNO4GRAPH Final Demonstration (<i>see Figure 11</i>)	Participation	Oct-23

CEA, ENEA	MICADO 2nd GA	Participation and poster session	Jan-22
CSM SPA	"INNOVATION IN NUCLEAR SAFETY: DESIGN, EXPERIENCE AND LESSONS LEARNED" PIACE (H2020) FINAL WORKSHOP	Presentation on "Next generation of experimental facilities. The advantages of the digital twin." (including CLEANDEM) by Egidio Zanin	Nov-22

2.1.3 CLEANDEM Final Workshop

The CLEANDEM Final Workshop has been a crucial Milestone for the project, which has allowed to gather almost 80 stakeholders to demonstrate them the CLEANDEM results. The event proved to be a success following on the positive feedback of the audience and on the improved statistics on LinkedIn (see Paragraph 3.1).

All details related to the event, including its agenda, are provided in D9.4.

Figure 1: CLEANDEM UGV's Final Demonstration

Figure 2: The CLEANDEM Final Workshop participants

2.2 Publications

In order to facilitate the dissemination of the project results among experts, it is also essential to refer to the publications made by project partners. The table below provides an overview, while further information for retrieving them will be provided in the dedicated section of the EU portal for the final reporting.

Partner	Type	Title	Authors	Title of the journal or equivalent
CEA	Article in journal	European collaborative efforts to achieve effective, safe, and cost-controlled dismantling of nuclear facilities	Nicolas Malleron, Michèle Guerin, Damien Roulet, Maugan Michel, Cédric Rivier, Philippe Lefevre and Marie-Bénédicte Jacques	EPJ N - Nuclear Sciences & Technologies
CEA	Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	CLEANDEM, a Cyber physical Equipment for unManned Nuclear DEcommissioning Measurements	Maugan Michel, Vincent Schoepff, Guillaume Amoyal, Luigi Lepore, Paolo Finocchiaro	ANIMMA 2023 Proceedings
CEA	Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Update on the cleandem project	Maugan Michel, Guillaume Amoyal, Vincent Schoepff, on behalf of the CLEANDEM consortium	DigiDecom2023 Proceedings
CEA	Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	CLEANDEM, a Cyber physical Equipment for unManned Nuclear DEcommissioning Measurements	Maugan Michel, Guillaume Amoyal, Vincent Schoepff, on behalf of the CLEANDEM consortium	DigiDecom2023 Proceedings
CEA	Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	CLEANDEM project – Final results	Maugan Michel, Guillaume Amoyal, Vincent Schoepff, on behalf of the CLEANDEM consortium	DigiDecom2024 Proceedings
ENEA	Article in journal	Design and test of a new prototype system for the air contamination monitoring	M. Capogni, L. Lepore, L. Silvi, M. Capone, P. De Felice, N. Cherubini, L. Carrarelli, A. Fazio, C. Di Ianni, M. Santucciono, A. Ferrari, S. Albin, P.	Sensors

			Sanna, F. Bondavalli	
ENEA	Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	A new prototype system for producing pure CO2 of interest for radiocarbon measurements	M. Capogni, L. Lepore, P. De Felice, N. Cherubini, A. Ferrari, L. Silvi, M. Capone, S. Albin	Book of Abstract
INFN	Article in journal	The Gamma and Neutron Sensor System for Rapid Dose Rate Mapping in the CLEANDEM Project	Fabio Rossi, Luigi Cosentino, Fabio Longhitano, Saverio Minutoli, Paolo Musico, Mikhail Osipenko, Gaetano Elio Poma, Marco Ripani, and Paolo Finocchiaro	Sensors
INFN	Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Hot-spots finding with modular gamma-ray system for sort and segregate activities	Gaetano Elio Poma, Luigi Cosentino, Fabio Longhitano and Paolo Finocchiaro	EPJ Web of Conferences
INFN	Article in journal	New technologies for radioactive waste monitoring: Results and perspectives from recent experience	P. Finocchiaro, L. Cosentino, G. E. Poma, F. Longhitano, S. Amaducci, G. Vecchio	IL NUOVO CIMENTO C
INFN	Article in journal	6LiF Converters for Neutron Detection: Production Procedures and Detector Tests	Antonio Massara, Gaetano Elio Poma, Simone Amaducci, Luigi Cosentino, Fabio Longhitano, Carmelo Marchetta, Martina Ursino, and Paolo Finocchiaro	Instruments
INFN	Article in journal	A Scintillator Array Table with Spectroscopic Features	Fabio Longhitano, Gaetano Elio Poma, Luigi Cosentino and Paolo Finocchiaro	Sensors
INFN	Article in journal	Providing better radiation monitoring for nuclear waste	Paolo Finocchiaro	Research Outreach

INFN	Thesis/dissertation	Study for a toolbox probes for UGV platform in D&D	S. Moretto	Research Outreach
INFN	Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Operations	Matteo Polo, Sandra Moretto, Daniela Fabris	THE EUROPEAN physical JOURNAL
INFN	Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Neutron-gamma survey system for decommissioning and dismantling activities	Erica Fanchini, Alessandro Iovane, Daniela Fabris and Sandra Moretto	THE EUROPEAN physical JOURNAL
TECNALIA	Article in journal	Modular and reconfigurable AMR for flexible inspection tasks in nuclear sites (<i>tentative</i>)	Ivan Villaverde, Arkaitz Urquiza	<i>To be Defined</i>

3 Communication activities

The communication implemented throughout CLEANDEM has aimed to be thought of as increasing the public visibility of the project and its results using accessible language. In order to make it possible, the CLEANDEM project partners have planned and implemented the communication activities detailed in the following sub-paragraphs.

3.1 Web communication

The public website, accessible under the URL www.cleandem-h2020.eu, has been the welcome page for the project, whereas the [LinkedIn account](#) created in September 2021 has become the tool to present the project outcomes and major on-going activities to a wider audience. Both were set-up and managed by CEA and ARTTIC.

The most successful social media campaign carried out by the CLEANDEM consortium has been a video interviews series taken by the project partners during the Technical Week held at the AiNT GmbH Technical Center, in Germany, from the 29th of January to the 2nd of February 2024. The aim was to introduce the visitors to the CLEANDEM project and to the technologies developed throughout its duration, 10 video interviews have been posted from the 5th of March until the 10th of April, paving the way to the CLEANDEM Final Workshop held at the SOGIN EUREX Plant in Saluggia in April 2024.

The CLEANDEM social media strategy has proven to be successful, as shown by the figures below showing the LinkedIn “page view”, “clicks”, “reactions” and “impressions” during the last year of the project implementation up to the aforementioned Final Workshop. It is here essential to specify that the “impressions” refers to the total number of views when the content is at least 50% on screen for at least 300ms, or the total number of times the content is clicked on, whichever comes first.

Figure 3: CLEANDEM LinkedIn - Page view

Figure 4: CLEANDEM LinkedIn - Clicks

Figure 5: CLEANDEM LinkedIn - Reactions

Figure 6: CLEANDEM LinkedIn - Impressions

Concerning the kind of visitors, the figures below show the kind of visitor that have been more attracted by the CLEANDEM LinkedIn page, classified on the basis of kind of industry, company size, job function and seniority of the visitors.

Figure 7: CLEANDEM LinkedIn - Visitors' industry

Figure 8: CLEANDEM LinkedIn - Visitors' company size

Figure 9: Visitors' job function

Figure 10: CLEANDEM LinkedIn - Visitors' seniority

3.2 Visual identity and communication material

Apart from setting-up and managing the CLEANDEM website and LinkedIn page, CEA and ARTTIC developed and produced the project visual identity for the project consortium. The CLEANDEM visual identity, considered at the core of the CLEANDEM D&C strategy, was distributed during the aforementioned events. Building on easily recognisable and attractive logo (designed by CAEN) and colours, the CLEANDEM visual identity has been then adapted to the following formats :

- [Leaflet](#),
- [Poster](#),
- [Roll-up banner](#),
- PPT and report templates, such as the one of this document,
- Flask, visible in Figure 11: CLEANDEM Project Partners at the Poster session of the INNO4GRAPH International Symposium Figure 11.

As an example, the picture below shows how the CLEANDEM project partners made use of the produced communication material for sponsoring the project results: CEA, SOGIN and ARTTIC representatives joined the INNO4GRAPH International Symposium at the EDF Industrial Demonstrator in Beaumont-en-Véron, France, in October 2023. During the event, a poster session dedicated to the CLEANDEM project was guaranteed, and the CLEANDEM communication material was distributed to the participants. Namely, the CLEANDEM flasks are visible in the picture below.

Figure 11: CLEANDEM Project Partners at the Poster session of the INNO4GRAPH International Symposium

Finally, it is also essential to underline that Ansaldo NUCLEARE produced and shared with the consortium a flyer presentation on “Enhanced Technologies applied to Decommissioning” in May 2024, that TECNALIA produced in March 2024 a promotional video of the success stories carried out during 2023 by TECNALIA’s Robotics KET, including a mention to CLEANDEM, and that SOGIN referred to CLEANDEM in the SOGIN annual Sustainability Report throughout the whole project duration.

3.3 Webinars and seminars

The CLEANDEM partners are aware that education and information are at the core of de-risking any kind of innovative solution. This is why many efforts have been dedicated to show the CLEANDEM results to students and/or specific user communities through webinars and dedicated lectures, as shown in the table below.

Participating partners	Communication activity name	Description	When
Orano DS	CLEANDEM Webinar	Online lecture	Feb-23
CAEN	CAEN Winter School	School for University students	Feb-24
CAEN	CLEANDEM Webinar	Online lecture	Feb-23
INFN	CLEANDEM webinar	Online lecture	Feb-23
INFN	10 seminars at high school	Seminars	May-22 May-23
SOGIN	Decommissioning summer school (2023 and 2024 edition)	School for University students	Jul-23 Jun-24
CSM SPA	CLEANDEM Webinar	Online lecture	Feb-23
AiNT	CLEANDEM Webinar	Online lecture	Sept-22 Feb-23
Orano DS	CLEANDEM Webinar	Online lecture	Feb-23

4 Conclusion

This report has detailed all the D&C activities implemented and planned by the project partners during the CLANDEM lifecycle.

In fact, the consortium has intended and intends to contribute to the exploitation of the project results and learnings by a much larger scope of stakeholders than the project consortium. Therefore, in order to address societal, industrial, scientific and political challenges in the D&D domain, the foreground knowledge has been communicated and disseminated throughout the whole project lifecycle and the consortium has already planned the D&C activities envisaged after the project end.

It is also essential to remind that the foreground knowledge has been communicated and disseminated throughout the project duration according to FAIR principles and building on the vision of open access to publications and, to the extent possible, data, following the scope of the CLEANDEM Data Management Plan (D10.4). In fact, the CLEANDEM project partners have resorted to the [Zenodo repository](#) for sharing the CLEANDEM outputs and results with larger audiences.

Within this framework, this report has aimed to detail all the D&C activities implemented and planned by the project partners during the CLANDEM lifecycle.

